

of number of silvershoots to tillers/50 hills at 30, 40, 50, 60, and 70 d after transplanting (DT). GM incidence also was measured at 50 DT on FARO 27, FARO 29, and ITA212 transplanted 20 Aug, 25 Sep, and 25 Oct.

Early-maturing FARO 27 was more

prone to GM infestation at 30-50 DT and medium-maturing FARO 29 at 40-60 DT (see table). The later the transplanting date, the higher the GM incidence (see figure). But many local farmers avoid early planting because they grow upland crops before rice. □

Effect of planting time on GM incidence. Edozhigi, Nigeria, 1985 wet season.

Host plants for yellow rice borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas* and white stem borer (WSB) *S. innotata*

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We measured YSB and WSB survival on two weed species common in ricefields. Individually caged plants of *Cyperus rotundus* and *Cynodon dactylon* were infested separately with newly emerged first-instar YSB and

WSB larvae.

On *C. rotundus*, both YSB and WSB larvae bored into the stem, fed on the inner contents, and pupated below the soil surface. Survival on *C. rotundus* was 78% for YSB and 53% for WSB.

On *C. dactylon*, the larvae scraped the inflorescence peduncle, fed a little on the inner stem contents, but failed to pupate. It could be that stem borer larvae initially feed on *C. dactylon*, then migrate to a newly transplanted rice crop. □

Walking the rice paddy for pest sampling does not affect yield

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It is necessary to walk the rice paddy to sample insect populations. We measured

the effect on yield of walking in the paddy.

Variety IR64 was transplanted 20 d after seeding at 25 × 25 cm. The field was divided into 24 plots measuring 2 × 5 m each. Four treatments (see table) were replicated six times in a

randomized complete block design.

There was no significant difference in yield. □

Effect on yield of walking through rice paddy. IRRI. 1986.

Walking (no./wk)	Yield (t/ha)
0 ^a	2.5
1	2.5
3	2.5
6	2.4

^aPlots not walked on 14-77 d after transplanting.

Occurrence of a virulent rice gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae* Wood-Mason biotype(?) in Andhra Pradesh, India

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During the 1986 wet season, GM severely damaged rice crops in northeastern Andhra Pradesh, where large tracts were planted to GM-resistant varieties Phalguna (RPW 6-17) and Surekha (developed from IR8/ Siam 29). These varieties were released in 1977 and 1976.

We assessed damage in cooperation with the extension staff of the Department of Agriculture, Andhra Pradesh.

Damage in Phalguna and Surekha averaged more than 50% silvershoots. Maximum damage approached 96%.

Susceptible varieties were severely damaged — CR1014, 33%; Mahsuri, 57%; RNR17, 78%; Sona, 84%; and Swarna, 88%.

Pest buildup was probably favored by high rainfall (410 mm) late Jun to mid-Aug, and frequent cyclonic storms in Sep and Oct, resulting in cloudy and humid periods. Farmers also were not familiar with control measures because GM had not occurred severely for more than 10 yr. Studies over 10 yr under the AICRIP coordinated entomology program have established 3 distinct biotypes, based on reactions to differential donors Eswarakora and